

EFFECTS OF MODERATE OXYGEN ENRICHMENT ($\leq 25\% \text{ O}_2$) ON FLAME STRUCTURE AND NO_x FORMATION IN INDUSTRIAL AIR FUEL BURNERS

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Introduction

- **Direct injection of oxygen** in the combustion air is a **simple means to increase thermal performance** of combustion systems, reducing the amount of nitrogen in the system,
- ISO 13577-2 (Industrial furnaces and associated processing equipment — Safety — Part 2: Combustion and fuel handling systems) requires **specific attention for concentrations above 25 % of oxygen in the combustion air.**
- **Advantages**
 - Significant **gain in thermal efficiency**,
 - **Low investment costs (CAPEX).**
- **Disadvantage**
 - For most burners, (very) strong **increase of NO_x emissions.**

Example data from reheating furnace tests (conventional configuration): up to +270 % increase in NO_x emissions

Numerical and experimental studies

New lateral burner developed for steel reheating furnaces:

- Numerically optimised,
- Capacity ranging from 1 to 6 MW,
- Tested experimentally in a semi-industrial scale furnace (1400 kW),
- Operating in a highly diluted (flameless) combustion mode for optimal heating and low NO_x performance with natural gas (NG) and hydrogen.

Experimental setup: Horizontal furnace (1400 kW), thermocouples, flow and pressure measurements, gas analysers.

1.4 MW test furnace

Wide flame concept

Scheme of the test furnace

- Roof thermocouples
- Waste gas analysis
- Access for IFRF type cooled probe
- Water cooled load

Fives Stein test furnace characteristics	
Power output	up to 1500 kW
Air factor	0.9 – 1.2
Air temperature	up to 650 °C
Furnace temperature	up to 1300 °C
Dimensions	6 x 3 x 2 m

Experimental results

Tests in a semi-industrial furnace:

Flame		Short flame		Long flame	
Furnace Temperature	°C	1217		1230	
Oxygen	% vol.	20,9	25	20,9	25
Power	kW	1402	1293	1408	1293
Efficiency gain	%	-	7,8	-	8,2
NO_x	mg/Nm ³ @ 3% O ₂ dry	40	41	35	38

- **NO_x variation is very low (<10 %)** in both short and long flame modes despite higher flame temperatures,
- A highly diluted wide flame suppresses NO_x formation even with direct oxygen enrichment,
- **The axial thermal profile of the flame is preserved** with oxygen enrichment, in long and short flame mode

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Conclusions

In some cases, industrial burners with highly diluted combustion can allow the use of direct injection of oxygen in the combustion air, below 25 %, without major modifications:

- Improving the thermal efficiency of the system, thus reducing the carbon footprint, of new and/or existing systems,
- Without increasing NO_x emissions.